

STUDENT MOTIVATION USING THE COMMUNICATIVE-COGNITIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. Within the given article the role of psychological feature ways in teaching English as a far-off language is analyzed. It shows the main sorts and factors, that are developed in fashionable teaching methodology.

Keywords: curriculum, instrumental incentives, learners' expectancy, motivation.

It's critical to align the teaching methodology with the objectives of the entire educational system in order to foster a psychologically engaging environment in English classes. In these circumstances, the role of the educator or pedagogue in the classroom is linked to entirely different method surveys. However, this method creates a very psychologically charged environment in English language learning classes. According to Smith, a renowned methodologist, "encouraging children could be an elementary part of what it's to be a teacher". The following primary categories and factors comprise the motivating techniques used in teaching English as a foreign language:

- Creating the essential conditions for motivation: Behaving like a teacher and building rapport with the students;
- creating a pleasant and secure environment in the room;
- non-group action and poor attendance;
- a frequent expression of reading that faculty is boring and moot
- apathetic non
- -participation within the classroom;

- -promoting favorable self-conception of foreign acquisition competence;
- making learner autonomy;
- adopting an active coming together role (by the teacher);
- -raising the learners' awareness of motivation maintenance strategies;
- feeling control;
- -motivation control.

Many academics worry about their students' motivation. A perfect classroom is one in which the students are engaged with the material being taught and demonstrate a desire to learn. While some pupils have these attributes, others do not. Lack of interest and desire can negatively impact student achievement levels, enjoyment, and creativity. Motivation, and more especially the diminishing levels of students' intrinsic motivation to learn, is a major worry for many educators. Some classrooms exude achievement, and some teachers motivate. It doesn't appear that motivation trends will always go downhill. The intrinsic motivation of a student to learn can be enhanced through a study plan and tutorial approaches. The lives of children are complex, and numerous factors contribute to academic success, such as intergenerational education.

Modern education is a complex system that requires an integrated approach to student motivation. One of the most effective methods of stimulating learning activity is the communicative and cognitive approach.

The communicative and cognitive approach in education involves the development of student's communication skills and cognitive functions through active interaction with teachers and peers. This approach includes a variety of learning methods, such as dialogues, discussions, group projects, and games, which contribute not only to the acquisition of knowledge but also to the development of the ability to communicate, analyze information, make decisions, and think creatively.

One of the key features of the communicative and cognitive approach is the active participation of students in the educational process. Thanks to the opportunity to discuss and analyze the material in a group, students get the opportunity to express their opinions, share ideas, and discuss issues with teachers and peers. This not only contributes to deeper assimilation of educational material but also motivates students to independently search for knowledge and research the topic.

Another important aspect of the communicative and cognitive approach is the individualization of the educational process. Taking into account the diversity of individual abilities, needs, and interests of students, the teacher should flexibly approach the organization of the educational process, using various teaching methods and an individual approach to each student.

Thus, the communicative and cognitive approach is an effective tool for stimulating students' learning motivation. By allowing them to actively participate in the learning process, discuss and analyze material in a group, as well as individualize the educational process, this approach contributes not only to the development of communicative and cognitive skills but also to the formation of interest in learning and constant self-development.

Conclusion

To sum up, motivation is counted as one of the most important factors in the English language teaching system in developing students' language proficiency. It could be created by the help of focusing on the integrative, anticipated intrinsic pleasure of learning

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